

Next-Generation Dry Powder Inhalers: Advances in Characterization and Evolving Regulatory Frameworks

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ABSTRACT

Dry powder inhalers (DPIs) have emerged as a vital platform for pulmonary drug delivery, offering targeted deposition, improved patient compliance, and enhanced formulation stability. As DPI technologies continue to advance, comprehensive characterization and regulatory alignment are essential to ensure therapeutic efficacy and patient safety. In this review covered an in-depth overview of in vitro performance testing of DPIs, including delivered dose uniformity, aerodynamic particle size distribution, fine particle dose, fine particle fraction, emitted dose, and inhaler resistance. Also covered recent advances in analytical methodologies, emphasizing their significance in predicting ex vivo and in vivo performance and maintaining batch-to-batch consistency. Discussed the regulatory framework through the perspective of the FDA's draft guidance on metered dose inhaler and dry powder inhaler drug products, particularly focusing on requirements for chemistry, manufacturing, and controls documentation, as well as bioequivalence assessment through in vitro and in vivo approaches. This review presents a comprehensive list of commercially available DPI products, along with product-specific guidance that outlines relevant FDA requirements. Furthermore, the review addresses critical aspects of stability testing and human factors engineering, underlining their roles in product lifecycle management and patient-centered design. This article combines scientific and regulatory viewpoints, and describes the evolution of DPIs in compliance with global quality and safety criteria.

Keywords: Dry powder inhalers, Advanced characterization, Stability studies, product-specific guidance, Regulatory framework.

INTRODUCTION

Pulmonary drug delivery has emerged as a pivotal route of administration for both local and systemic therapies, offering several clinical and therapeutic advantages. The lungs provide a large surface area, thin alveolar epithelium, and extensive vascularization, enabling rapid drug absorption and onset of action. This route minimizes first-pass metabolism and allows for lower systemic exposure, which can reduce adverse effects compared to oral or parenteral administration. Additionally, inhalation-based therapies tend to improve patient adherence due to their non-invasive nature and ease of use, making them particularly suitable for chronic disease management^{1, 2}.

Among the various inhalation platforms, dry powder inhalers (DPIs) have gained substantial attention owing to their intrinsic benefits, including better chemical and physical stability of formulations, ease of handling and transportation, and elimination of environmentally harmful propellants used in pressurized metered-dose inhalers (pMDIs). These features make DPIs an attractive choice for both pharmaceutical developers and healthcare systems. Clinically, DPIs have become a mainstay in the treatment of respiratory disorders such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and they are now being explored for systemic drug delivery, including peptides, proteins, and vaccines broadening their application beyond traditional respiratory indications^[3].

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The development of next-generation DPIs is being driven by several converging factors: the need to enhance drug deposition efficiency in the deep lung, improve ease of use across diverse patient populations (including children, elderly, and those with reduced lung function), and ensure consistent performance under variable real-world conditions [4]. However, designing and evaluating DPIs is inherently complex. The final product performance is influenced by a multifactorial interaction between formulation characteristics (such as particle size, morphology, and flow properties), device design parameters (like airflow resistance and dispersion mechanisms), and patient-specific factors, notably the inspiratory flow rate and technique [5,6,7]. This complexity necessitates thorough and reproducible testing during development and quality control stages.

In this context, robust *in vitro* performance testing becomes indispensable. Parameters such as delivered dose uniformity (DDU), aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD), fine particle dose (FPD), fine particle fraction (FPF), emitted dose (ED), and inhaler resistance are critical in assessing the consistency and efficiency of drug delivery. These measurements also serve as surrogates to predict *in vivo* performance, thereby aiding in the optimization of both formulation and device design.

Simultaneously, the regulatory landscape for DPIs is evolving. Regulatory authorities, including the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), have issued updated guidance documents requiring compliance with both pharmaceutical quality and device performance standards and emphasizing the importance of chemistry, manufacturing, and controls (CMC) documentation, robust bioequivalence (BE) assessment strategies, and the incorporation of patient-centric design principles [2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9]. There is an increasing expectation for DPI products especially generics to demonstrate equivalency not only through pharmacokinetic endpoints but also through *in vitro* performance metrics and human factors validation.

This review aims to provide a comprehensive and up-to-date overview of the current landscape and future directions in DPI characterization. It highlights recent advancements in analytical characterization techniques, product-specific guidance outlining

relevant regulatory requirements, and critical aspects such as stability studies, *in vivo* evaluations, and human factors testing. By synthesizing scientific progress with regulatory trends, this review offers a unified perspective on the development of next-generation dry powder inhalers that are not only effective and safe but also aligned with patient needs and global regulatory expectations.

INDUSTRY ADAPTED DPI MANUFACTURING AND CHARACTERIZATION TECHNOLOGIES:

DPI manufacturing involves precise powder blending to ensure uniform drug distribution, typically using tumble blenders, high-shear mixers, and continuous mixers. General DPI scale-up challenges include maintaining content uniformity, managing static charge, and ensuring consistent powder flow. Adaption of high-precision blending systems to ensure content uniformity of drug and carrier [4]. The industry has evolved from simple inhalation devices to sophisticated systems capable of targeted pulmonary drug delivery. Advanced manufacturing and processing technologies include cutting-edge methods for formulating, mixing, and filling DPI medications have become essential to meet regulatory, quality, and patient-centric design standards [5, 6]. Advanced DPI formulations rely on sophisticated particle engineering techniques such as micronization, spray drying, co-spray drying or composite particle design, and supercritical fluid methods. These techniques are essential for reducing particle size to the optimal aerodynamic diameter range of 1–5 μm , enabling the production of highly uniform particles, enhancing flowability, and providing precise control over particle morphology and size [6]. Another critical aspect of DPI formulation is blending and homogenization, which ensures the uniform distribution of the drug and carrier materials. Commonly used equipment for this purpose includes tumble blenders, high-shear mixers, and continuous mixing systems. The final stage of DPI manufacturing involves automated filling systems. High-speed filling lines are designed to be compatible with various DPI formats, including capsule-based, blister-based, and reservoir-type devices, ensuring efficiency and consistency in large-scale production [7, 8].

Traditional Physico-Chemical, Advanced Polymorphic and Morphological Evaluation of DPI Powder Particles: Traditional physicochemical, advanced polymorphic, and morphological evaluations of DPI powder particles are summarized in Table 1, with detailed characterizations provided in the following sections.

Table1: Comprehensive characterization techniques of dry powder inhalations at different stages of fabrication

Parameter	Purpose	Method
Physicochemical Properties of the Powder		
Particle size	Particle size distribution of powders (API or carrier) impacts lung deposition, API particle size ideal requirement is 1–5 μm	Laser diffraction Mastersizer 3000+ Ultra by Malvern
Imaging Techniques for Morphology and Surface Properties	Morphology influence aerodynamic behaviour during aerosolization, affecting drag forces, terminal velocity, and ultimately, deposition within the respiratory tract	Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-ray Powder Diffraction (XRPD) & Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM).
Surface area	Particle surface area plays a pivotal role in powder behavior, particularly in terms of cohesion, dispersion, and stability.	Brunauer Emmett Teller (BET) analytical technique
Crystallinity/amorphous	Affects stability and solubility. Different polymorphic forms can exhibit distinct physical and chemical properties, even though they have the same chemical composition.	X-ray Diffraction (XRD), modulated DSC, FTIR and Raman Spectroscopy
Hygroscopicity	Moisture uptake can impair performance. Small amounts of moisture can significantly affect powder flow, stability, aerosolization, and lung deposition.	Dynamic Vapour Sorption (DVS)
Density	Affects aerodynamic properties	Tapped/True Density Measurement
Powder Flow Properties		
Bulk and tapped density	Provides the flow and evaluates compressibility of the powder	Volumetric analysis; Bulk / Tapped Density Measurement
Angle of repose	Indicates the flow behaviour of the powder	Funnel method
Carr's index & Hausner ratio	Provides the flowability of the powder	Based on bulk/tapped density
Moisture content	Higher content of moisture can significantly affect powder flow, stability, aerosolization, and lung deposition.	Karl Fisher Method
In vitro performance testing		
Aerodynamic Particle Size Distribution (APSD)	Determine the size range of aerosolized particles, which affects deposition in different regions of the lungs.	NGI, ACI, TOF Spectrometry
Emitted Dose (ED)	Assess the total dose released from the inhaler upon actuation	Dose Uniformity Tester, HPLC
Inhaler Resistance and Flow Dependency	Evaluate how inhaler design affects airflow resistance and performance across different user profiles	Pressure drop at flow rates
Powder Dispersion and De-agglomeration	Evaluate how well the DPI disperses the powder formulation into fine, respirable particles	Laser diffraction, imaging; High-Speed Imaging & Particle Tracking
Chemical Assay and Content Uniformity	Ensure consistent API content in each delivered dose and across the batch	HPLC, UPLC

Parameter	Purpose	Method
Hygroscopicity and Environmental Stability Testing	Evaluate DPI performance under varied humidity and temperature conditions	Controlled Environment Chamber Testing; Dynamic Vapor Sorption (DVS)
Patient-Use Simulation (Human Factors & Real-World Use)	Understand real-world device usability and performance under varied patient conditions	Use of spirometry; Inhalation Profile Recording & Usability Studies

Powder Flow Properties:

Powder flow properties are significantly influenced by particle characteristics such as shape, surface roughness, and size distribution, all of which can present handling challenges and impose limitations during industrial processes like capsule or container filling. To improve the bulk properties of powder formulations used in DPIs, a common strategy involves blending the micronized active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) with a carrier typically a coarse excipient particle, most often lactose monohydrate, with a particle size range of 50 to 200 μm . In such formulations, the carrier generally constitutes more than 90% of the total mixture. This approach results in an ordered mixture, or adhesive blend, where the fine API particles adhere to the surface of the larger carrier particles, enhancing flowability and dispersion upon inhalation [10].

Dry powder inhalers depend on the flow properties of the powder formulation for accurate and consistent dosing. Critical parameters include bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner ratio, and angle of repose, all of which help evaluate flow characteristics essential for efficient lung delivery. Bulk density refers to the mass of a powder divided by its total volume, including interstitial spaces, and influences dose uniformity, flowability, packing, and dispersion. Tapped density is the increased bulk density achieved after mechanical tapping, reducing void volume and improving packing [10, 11]. The difference between bulk and tapped density reflects powder compressibility and flowability, with larger differences indicating poorer flow. Carr's Index and Hausner Ratio assess powder flowability by comparing bulk and tapped densities, helping evaluate the handling characteristics of pharmaceutical powders. The angle of repose, indicating the steepest angle at which a powder pile remains stable, is another key measure of flow. Powders with a high angle of repose typically exhibit poor flow, which can affect

blending, compression, and capsule filling. In dry powder inhalers, good powder flow is essential for accurate dosing, efficient capsule filling, and consistent aerosolization.

Moisture Content:

Moisture content is a critical factor influencing the performance of dry powder inhalers. DPIs deliver medication as dry, micronized particles, even small amounts of moisture can significantly affect powder flow, stability, aerosolization, and lung deposition. High humidity can lead to increased interparticulate forces, causing agglomeration and reducing the amount of drug available for inhalation. This can negatively impact the emitted dose and respirable fraction, potentially diminishing the effectiveness of the medication [11]. Dynamic Vapor Sorption (DVS) is a sophisticated analytical technique used to investigate the impact of moisture on the cohesion and flow behavior of DPI formulations by precisely measuring water sorption at controlled relative humidity conditions. The presence of moisture can promote capillary condensation and strengthen interparticle interactions, which negatively influences powder dispersibility and aerodynamic performance. Recent advancements in DVS methodologies such as humidity cycling and prolonged exposure protocols enable comprehensive evaluation of the long-term hygroscopic stability, potential phase transitions, and overall performance reliability of DPI formulations under conditions that closely simulate real-world storage and use.

Particle Morphology and Surface Area:

The efficacy of aerosolized drug delivery to the deep lung is highly dependent on the morphology and surface characteristics of the particles, particularly those of the carrier in dry powder inhaler systems. Particle shape and structure influence aerodynamic behavior during aerosolization, affecting drag forces,

terminal velocity, and ultimately, deposition within the respiratory tract. Various studies have shown that carrier particles with specific morphologies can significantly enhance drug delivery to the lower airways (Figure 1). In particular, low-density, pollen-shaped carriers have demonstrated improved pulmonary deposition due to their extended drug-binding capabilities and favorable aerodynamic properties [12,13,14]. The surface area of particles plays a pivotal role in powder behavior, particularly in terms of cohesion, dispersion, and stability. Given the small size of aerosolized particles, the cumulative surface area of DPI powders is typically very high, increasing their susceptibility to electrostatic charging, moisture absorption, and van der Waals forces. Larger specific surface areas lead to stronger cohesive interactions due to increased van der Waals forces. This can result in poor flowability and suboptimal aerosolization, ultimately compromising dose uniformity and delivery efficiency. To mitigate these effects, excipient carriers such as lactose are used to reduce cohesion and improve flow characteristics [15]. Advanced analytical techniques such as Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), and X-ray Microtomography (Micro-CT) are widely employed to characterize particle morphology and surface topography in dry powder inhaler (DPI) formulations. Among these, Micro-CT offers high-resolution three-dimensional imaging, allowing for non-destructive analysis of internal particle structure and spatial distribution, thereby providing critical insights into formulation architecture and performance attributes [14,15, 16].

Figure 1: Schematic representation of particle deposition and absorption in the respiratory tract following DPI actuation

Morphological Considerations in API-Carrier Blending:

In general, a carrier-based DPI formulations, the process begins with blending the API with a carrier, typically lactose. The detachment of the API from the carrier during inhalation is critically influenced by particle morphology specifically, parameters such as elongation ratio (ER), roundness (RO), surface roughness, and shape. Particles with higher ER and RO values tend to exhibit irregular and rough morphologies, which can enhance aerosol performance by promoting effective detachment of the API. However, these irregularities may also negatively impact powder flowability and manufacturability. Hence, a balance must be achieved between optimal aerosolization and processability. Because morphology and size are interrelated, both parameters must be evaluated in tandem during formulation development [14]. Surface modification techniques such as spray drying can be used to engineer rougher API surfaces, reducing contact area with the carrier and thereby improving detachment and increasing the fine particle fraction (FPF). Raman mapping is a powerful analytical technique that facilitates the spatially resolved identification and distribution of APIs and carriers within individual particles of DPI formulations. Complementarily, Synchrotron-based X-ray Powder Diffraction provides ultra-high-resolution detection of crystalline forms, enabling precise polymorph characterization and differentiation, which are critical for ensuring the stability, efficacy, and quality of DPI products.

Polymorphism in Dry Powder Inhalers:

Polymorphism is an ability of a drug substance that enables to exist in more than one crystalline form. These different polymorphic forms can display different physical and chemical properties despite of having the same chemical composition. Polymorphism can be analysed by several advanced characterization techniques, including X-Ray Powder Diffraction (XRPD), Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), and Raman Spectroscopy. The polymorphic state of a molecule in the solid phase has a direct impact on solubility, drug delivery performance, stability,

bioavailability, processability, and even regulatory approval. Solid-state phase transitions include polymorphic transformations as well as order disorder and disorder order conversions. Solid-state characterization and microscopy techniques

employed to study respirable therapeutic powders for DPIs are summarized in Table 2. Implementing robust analytical and process control measures is crucial to ensuring consistent product quality and therapeutic effectiveness [17, 18].

Table 2: List of solid-state characterization methods for particles in dry powder inhalers.

Characterization Methodology / Technique	Sample Type / states of matter	Working principle	Deliverables
Laser diffraction sizing	Dispersed solid	Mie theory works by measuring the angular distribution of light scattered by particles to determine their size distribution, which is critical for aerosol performance and lung deposition.	Mean diameter
Atomic force microscopy (AFM)	Solid	AFM works by scanning a sharp probe over particle surfaces to produce high-resolution topography and measure surface properties like roughness and adhesion, influencing particle and device interactions.	Surface roughness, Surface energy
Karl Fischer titration (KFT)	Solid	KFT works by chemically measuring the water content in samples, which is crucial for assessing moisture-related stability and aerosol performance.	Residual water content
Inverse gas chromatography (IGC)	Solid	IGC works by measuring surface energy and molecular interactions of particles through the retention behavior of probe gases, providing insight into cohesion, adhesion, and formulation stability.	Adsorption isotherm, Glass transition temperature, Surface energy of solids
Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)	Solid	DSC works by measuring heat flow associated with thermal transitions in particles, such as melting or crystallization, to assess polymorphism and stability.	T _{onset} T _{peak} J, Cp
Hot-stage microscopy (HSM)	Solid	HSM works by visually monitoring morphological and phase changes in particles under controlled heating, helping to assess thermal behavior, polymorphic transitions, and stability relevant to inhalation performance.	Crystallinity, Melting, Boiling
X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD)	Solid	XRPD works by identifying and quantifying the crystalline phases and polymorphic forms of drug and excipient particles, which influence aerosolization and drug delivery performance.	Diffraction pattern d-spacing
Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)	Solid	SEM works by using a focused electron beam to generate high-resolution images of particle morphology, size, and surface texture, aiding in the assessment of aerosolization behavior.	Particle size, Shape, Surface structure
Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)	Solid	TEM works by transmitting a beam of electrons through ultra-thin samples to produce high-resolution images of internal structures, aiding in the analysis of particle morphology and crystallinity.	Particle internal structure
X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)	Solid	XPS/EDS work by detecting elemental composition and chemical states on particle	Elemental analysis

Characterization Methodology / Technique	Sample Type / states of matter	Working principle	Deliverables
and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS)		surfaces, helping to analyze surface chemistry that influences drug delivery and stability.	
Raman ATR-FTIR	Solid	Raman ATR-FTIR work by detecting molecular vibrations to identify chemical composition and polymorphic forms, aiding in assessing drug-excipient interactions and stability.	Molecular fingerprint

IN VITRO PERFORMANCE TESTING OF DPI FORMULATIONS:

In vitro performance testing is essential for evaluating how effectively a dry powder inhaler delivers medication to the lungs. These tests simulate patient use and provide critical data on dose accuracy, aerosol quality, and particle behaviour, helping to ensure consistent, safe, and effective drug delivery.

Delivered Dose Uniformity (DDU):

DDU testing is a critical quality control measure used to ensure that each actuation of a DPI from the first to the last delivers a consistent and accurate amount of the API. This testing is essential for meeting regulatory requirements and maintaining FDA approval, as it verifies the reliability and performance of the inhalation device throughout its entire lifecycle. Standard DDU evaluation involves testing 10 separate inhaler units, with drug content determinations conducted at two distinct points: at the beginning and at the end of each unit's use. This results in a total of 20 determinations (2 per unit), providing robust data to assess dose consistency over time and across units [17]. While there is no universally fixed formula for DDU, the data are typically analyzed statistically to assess variability both within and between units, ensuring the product consistently meets predefined acceptance criteria.

Aerodynamic Particle Size Distribution (APSD):

APSD is a critical parameter in assessing the deposition behaviour of inhaled drug particles within the respiratory tract, directly impacting the therapeutic efficacy of DPI formulations. Particles with aerodynamic diameters between 1 and 5 μ m are generally considered optimal for deep lung deposition, as they can bypass the oropharyngeal region and reach the lower airways. APSD is influenced by multiple factors, including inhaler device design, particularly internal airflow resistance and powder dispersion mechanisms. Formulation characteristics such as particle size, morphology, density, and surface properties, and patient-related variables like inspiratory flow rate and inhalation pattern. To evaluate APSD, cascade impaction techniques are commonly used; instruments such as the Andersen Cascade Impactor (ACI) and the Next Generation Impactor (NGI) classify aerosol particles based on aerodynamic diameter by sequentially depositing them onto stages with defined cut-off sizes. Comparative evaluation between Andersen Cascade Impactor and Next Generation Impactor are tabulated in Table 3. These measurements allow for precise quantification of particle size distribution within the respirable range and are essential for meeting regulatory requirements in DPI product characterization.

Table 3: Comparative evaluation between Andersen Cascade Impactor and Next Generation Impactor

Category / Parameter	ACI (Andersen Cascade Impactor)	NGI (Next-Generation Pharmaceutical Impactor)
USP Status	USP Apparatus 1	USP Apparatus 5
Design & Format	Vertical stack of ~6–8 stages	Horizontal layout with 7 stages + Micro-Orifice Collector (MOC)
Testing Principle	Aerodynamic size separation based on inertial impaction	Same inertial principle with sharper efficiency curves across stages

Category / Parameter	ACI (Andersen Cascade Impactor)	NGI (Next-Generation Pharmaceutical Impactor)
Flow Rate Range	Originally calibrated at 28.3 L/min; DPI kits permit operation at 60 or 90 L/min	Fully validated at 15-100 L/min with precise interpolation for cut-off diameters
Pre-separator Compatibility	DPI testing requires separate high-capacity pre-separator installed between induction port and stage 0. Setup may vary by kit.	Built-in pre-separator support—standard configuration for DPI testing under USP <601>. Enhances separation of large carrier particles.
Number of stages	8 impactor stages + optional pre-separator + after-filter.	7 stages + Micro-Orifice Collector (MOC) + optional pre-separator + after-filter. Captures sub-micron particles in dedicated cup.
Mass Balance	Requires that recovery (sum of stage + filter + losses) fall within 85 %–115 % of emitted dose. Total wall losses must remain $\leq 5\%$.	Same requirements: issued dose recovery must be between 85 %–115 %; wall losses $< 5\%$. More readily met given optimized design
MMAD / GSD / FPF Output	MMAD typically between 1–5 μm ; GSD often 1.5–3.0; may overestimate FPF due to wall loss bias or stage overlap at high flow.	MMAD in $\sim 1\text{--}5\ \mu\text{m}$ range; GSD usually tighter ($< 1.2\text{--}2.0$ depending on formulation); sharper separation yields reproducible FPF.
Flow Control Importance	Critical to maintain $\pm 5\%$ flow accuracy for consistent stage cut-offs. Critical flow controllers needed at higher flows.	Similar requirements; maintained via precision critical-flow control—NGI's design reduces variability.
Stage Mensuration	Required regularly: each stage's jet dimensions must conform to specification; individual stage replacement allowed.	Required for whole instrument: if any stage out-of-spec, unit must be returned for correction. Calibration is archival.
Ease of Use	More labour-intensive due to vertical stacking; slower turn-around. Manual washing and setup.	User-friendly tray design, quick-clamp assembly, suited for semi-/fully automated recovery and high throughput preferred in regulated labs.

Cascade Impactors (e.g., Andersen, NGI):

Cascade impactors are analytical instruments used to determine aerodynamic particle size distribution by separating aerosol particles based on their aerodynamic diameter through inertial impaction. They are essential tools for characterizing inhaled pharmaceutical products, such as DPIs, metered-dose inhalers (MDIs), nebulizers, and nasal sprays. The system operates by directing an aerosol through a series of staged nozzles or orifices with progressively smaller cut-off diameters and increasing flow velocities. Particles with higher inertia (larger aerodynamic diameters) deposit on the earlier stages, while smaller particles proceed to later stages^[19]. This enables precise, size-resolved particle collection over a range typically from 0.01 to 10 μm , depending on the configuration.

Fine Particle Dose (FPD) and Fine Particle Fraction (FPF):

In inhalation drug delivery, FPF and FPD are key performance indicators used to assess the respirable portion of an aerosolized formulation, specifically, the fraction capable of reaching the lower respiratory tract and producing a therapeutic effect. FPF is defined as the percentage of the emitted dose composed of particles with an aerodynamic diameter less than 5 μm , a threshold commonly associated with particles that can bypass the upper airways and deposit in the lungs. While 5 μm is the standard cut-off, this threshold may vary depending on regulatory guidelines or study-specific requirements. FPF is a relative measure that reflects the efficiency of particle dispersion and the lung-targeting capability of a given formulation device combination^[20]. In contrast, FPD represents the absolute mass (typically in micrograms or milligrams) of particles within the emitted dose that have an aerodynamic diameter below 5 μm . This value provides a direct estimate of the drug amount likely to reach the respirable regions of the lungs. The FPD is

influenced by several aerodynamic particle properties, including geometric size, shape, density, and the patient's inhalation flow rate. Complementary aerodynamic metrics such as Mass Median Aerodynamic Diameter (MMAD) and Geometric Standard Deviation (GSD) are also critical for characterizing the full-size distribution of aerosol particles^[20]. Additional related parameters include the ED, the total amount of drug released from the inhaler and deposited in the impactor and the Emitted Fraction (EF), which quantifies the proportion of the nominal (loaded) dose that is emitted from the device. Together, FPF and FPD provide a comprehensive understanding of inhaler performance. FPF indicates how efficiently the device generates respirable particles, while FPD quantifies the actual dose available for pulmonary absorption. Both are essential for formulation development, device optimization, bioequivalence studies, and regulatory approval of Orally Inhaled Products (OIPs).

DissolvIt®: A biorelevant in-vitro Model for Pulmonary Drug Absorption:

DissolvIt is a mechanistically representative in vitro model designed to mimic drug dissolution and absorption at the air blood interface of the upper respiratory tract. The system comprises aerosolized particles deposited onto a glass coverslip, overlaid with a mucus simulant and a polycarbonate membrane that replicates the epithelial barrier. Below this barrier, an albumin-rich buffer is continuously perfused to simulate pulmonary blood flow. Test formulations are aerosolized and deposited using the PreciseInhale system, ensuring precise and reproducible dosing. Dissolution begins upon particle contact with the mucus layer and is monitored in real-time through optical microscopy by tracking particle disappearance. As the drug dissolves, it diffuses across the simulated barrier into the perfusate, where drug concentrations are quantified over time using LC-MS/MS. Residual drug retained in the barrier is also analyzed to ensure accurate mass balance. This setup enables detailed characterization of pulmonary dissolution kinetics and has demonstrated the ability to replicate in vivo-like absorption profiles. Consequently, DissolvIt serves as a valuable tool for predicting pharmacokinetic behaviour and supporting

in vitro–in vivo correlation (IVIVC) in inhalation drug development^[21].

EX VIVO LUNG TISSUE MODELS FOR DPI CHARACTERIZATION:

Ex vivo lung tissue models, particularly isolated and perfused lungs (IPL) and precision-cut lung slices (PCLS), provide physiologically relevant platforms for the characterization of DPIs, enabling the assessment of deposition, dissolution, absorption, and toxicity in a controlled yet biologically intact environment. The IPL model preserves the structural and functional integrity of the entire lung, allowing real-time monitoring of respiratory parameters, particle deposition, and drug absorption across the alveolar-capillary barrier under near-physiological conditions. Utilizing species such as rat, guinea pig, or rabbit, IPL systems maintain perfusion and ventilation, making them especially valuable for studying regional deposition and systemic uptake kinetics of inhaled formulations. In contrast, PCLS represent a microscale yet highly reproducible alternative, retaining the native cytoarchitecture and cellular diversity of the lung while enabling high-throughput screening^[22]. Prepared by slicing fixed, agarose-inflated lung lobes into uniform thin sections (typically 200–300 μm), PCLS allow localized exposure to DPI aerosols or drug solutions and support functional assays such as ciliary activity, bronchoconstriction, and inflammation. Importantly, both IPL and PCLS models bridge the gap between in vitro and in vivo approaches, offering enhanced translational relevance for preclinical evaluation of DPIs. Their use aids in elucidating drug-tissue interactions, optimizing particle design, and refining dosing strategies prior to animal or human studies.

Isolated and Perfused Lungs (IPL):

The isolated and perfused lung model is a widely used ex vivo system that enables detailed evaluation of pulmonary drug delivery, including deposition, absorption, and barrier interactions. The selection of animal species commonly rodents (rats, mice), guinea pigs, or rabbits is based on lung size, anatomical similarity to humans, ease of handling, and availability. Larger lungs (e.g., from rabbits or guinea pigs) are preferred when detailed sampling or aerosol administration is required. The methodology involves

excising the lungs with the trachea intact, followed by cannulation of the pulmonary artery and trachea to allow controlled perfusion with physiological buffer and ventilation with air or aerosolized drug formulations (Figure 2A). This setup maintains lung viability and function for several hours post-excision. Key advantages of the IPL model include preservation of lung architecture, physiological barrier integrity, and dynamic parameters like ventilation-perfusion matching, making it ideal for pharmacokinetic and mechanistic studies. However, limitations include technical complexity, limited experimental duration due to loss of viability over time, interspecies anatomical differences, and ethical considerations related to animal use. Additionally, the lack of immune and systemic influences restricts its utility in modelling long-term or whole-body responses.

Figure 2A: Schematic diagram of ex vivo lung tissue models. Isolated and perfused lungs (IPL) serve as physiologically relevant platforms for the characterization of dry powder inhalers

Precision-Cut Lung Slices (PCLS):

Precision-cut lung slices are an ex vivo model that preserves the complex cellular composition and 3D architecture of lung tissue, making them highly suitable for evaluating local effects of dry powder inhalers, including drug distribution, metabolism, and tissue response. Animal selection typically rodents (rats, mice), guinea pigs, or pigs is guided by lung size, anatomical similarity to human lungs, and tissue availability. Larger animals like pigs are preferred when larger slices or human-comparable anatomy is required. The methodology involves inflating excised lungs with low-melting agarose to maintain structure,

followed by tissue coring and slicing (typically 200–300 μm thick) using a precision tissue slicer (Figure 2B). PCLS remain viable for several days in culture, allowing repeated dosing and temporal studies. Advantages include reproducibility, high throughput, and the ability to perform diverse functional assays (e.g., bronchoconstriction, cytokine release, ciliary activity) in a well-preserved microenvironment. However, limitations include absence of perfusion and immune cell recruitment, limited lifespan compared to in vivo systems, and interspecies variability [22]. Additionally, slicing may disrupt some microvasculature or surface structures, and drug exposure is usually restricted to the apical side, potentially affecting distribution assessment.

Figure 2B: Schematic diagram of ex vivo lung tissue models. Precision-cut lung slices (PCLS) offer physiologically relevant platforms for the characterization of dry powder inhalers

BIOEQUIVALENCE (BE) AND IN VIVO STUDIES OF DPIS:

The development of **generic DPIs** for the treatment of **bronchial asthma** and **chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)** requires a rigorous demonstration of **bioequivalence** with the reference (innovator) product. The fundamental principles guiding this process emphasize the need for a comprehensive evaluation through **pharmaceutical equivalence**, **in vitro performance**, **pharmacokinetic (PK)** studies, and in some cases, **clinical endpoint** or **pharmacodynamic (PD)** assessments. Unlike systemically acting oral medications, DPIs deliver drugs directly to the lungs, making BE assessment more complex due to localized drug action. Consequently, a **weight-of-evidence**

approach is recommended by regulatory agencies such as the **FDA** and **EMA**. This approach integrates data from **in vitro characterization** (e.g., APSD, ED, and DDU) with **in vivo PK studies**, and where necessary, **PD** or **clinical endpoint trials** [23]. The acceptance criteria for bioequivalence, as defined by the regulatory body, are illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic representaion of acceptance criteria for bioequivalence as per the regulatory guidance

Pharmacokinetic studies, though they primarily measure **systemic drug concentrations**, serve as **surrogate markers** for pulmonary drug deposition. While systemic exposure may not directly reflect local lung deposition, PK data remain critical for evaluating absorption and comparing systemic exposure between the test and reference products. In cases where PK alone is insufficient, **clinical endpoint studies** or **PD evaluations** may be required to confirm therapeutic equivalence, currently commercialized marketed reference listed drug products (RLDs) and the corresponding regulatory equivalence requirements, as outlined in the FDA's product-specific guidance [24]. Furthermore, **imaging-based deposition studies**, such as **gamma scintigraphy**, may be employed to directly assess the distribution and regional deposition of the drug in the lungs, offering additional evidence of equivalence in pulmonary delivery. This multi-faceted evaluation strategy ensures that generic DPIs are **pharmaceutically and therapeutically equivalent**

to their reference counterparts, supporting their approval in terms of **efficacy**, **safety**, and **clinical performance** in the management of asthma and COPD.

STABILITY DATA REQUIREMENTS FOR DPI FORMULATIONS AND DEVICES:

The stability of dry powder inhalers is a critical aspect of the regulatory approval process, as it directly impacts the safety, efficacy, and quality of the drug product throughout its intended shelf life. Regulatory agencies such as the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), the European Medicines Agency (EMA), and other authorities following International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines specifically ICH Q1A(R2) and Q1B mandate comprehensive stability studies that address both the drug formulation and the device components. These studies must assess the integrated product, which consists of the active pharmaceutical ingredient and excipients combined within the inhaler device, under well-defined environmental conditions [25, 26]. The purpose is to demonstrate that the product maintains chemical stability (including API potency and degradation), physical stability (such as particle size distribution, flowability, and hygroscopicity), aerosol performance stability (including emitted dose, fine particle fraction, and aerodynamic particle size distribution), and device functionality (such as actuation performance, dose metering accuracy, and device integrity). Stability testing is typically performed under ICH-recommended storage conditions, which include long-term ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ / $60 \pm 5\%$ RH for up to 24 months), intermediate ($30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ / $65 \pm 5\%$ RH for 6 months), and accelerated ($40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ / $75 \pm 5\%$ RH for 6 months) conditions. For DPIs that are particularly sensitive to moisture, additional protective packaging and stress testing, such as open-device storage or low-humidity studies may be necessary to confirm the robustness and reliability of the product throughout its lifecycle.

Stability testing of DPI formulations is a **product-device integrated** evaluation that must ensure performance, safety, and quality over the intended shelf life. A robust stability program, aligned with ICH guidelines and specific inhalation product

considerations Table 4, is critical for regulatory approval.

Table 4: Stability parameters for DPI formulations and acceptance guidance

S No	Stability parameter for DPIs	Method	Specification
1	Particle size distribution	Laser diffraction or Cascade impaction	API: less than 5µm
2	Moisture content	Karl Fischer titration or loss on drying	The limit for moisture content should be established based on results seen in stability studies
3	Assay and degradation products	HPLC or UPLC	At release assay limits of ± 5%
4	Delivered dose uniformity	HPLC or UPLC	85 -115% (Flow rate range at 30 - 90L/min)
5	FPD	NGI or ACI	±25 % (Ranges wider than ±25% should be sufficiently justified by in vivo data). Flow rate range at 30-90L/min
6	Device performance	Dose delivery consistency, Actuation force	It depends on the inspiratory flow rate, inhalation time, acceleration rate, and inhalation volume.
7	Container–closure integrity	Especially for capsule- or blister-based DPIs	There are no specific limits of container closure integrity over shelf life.
8	Mechanical integrity and device robustness	Over repeated use or environmental stress (e.g., vibration, drop tests) must be shown	Shall be product specific
9	Dose counter functionality	Must remain accurate throughout the product's shelf life	For Multidose inhalation medicinal products each unit should have a dose counter to give the patient indication of when the number of actuations stated on the label has been delivered
10	Compatibility between the formulation and device materials	Must be evaluated to rule out leachables or sorption issues	Depending on the levels and types of compounds detected, consideration should be given to include a test and limits for leachables in the finished medicinal product specification.

REGULATORY CONSIDERATIONS FOR DPIS AND EMERGING EVIDENCE:

The current regulatory framework for submitting generic dry powder inhalers to the U.S. Food and Drug Administration is governed by the Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA) pathway, which requires evidence of therapeutic equivalence to the reference listed drug demonstrating comparable clinical efficacy and safety under labeled conditions of use (Figure 4). Due to the complexity of DPIS as drug-device combination products, the FDA adopts a "weight-of-evidence" approach to establish bioequivalence, incorporating in vitro studies (e.g.,

single actuation content and APSD), pharmacokinetic studies in healthy volunteers to assess systemic exposure, and pharmacodynamic or clinical endpoint studies in patients to evaluate local drug delivery and therapeutic outcomes [27, 28]. To guide sponsors, the FDA issues product-specific guidances (PSGs) detailing the recommended study designs and data requirements for ANDA submissions, ensuring a consistent and scientifically robust evaluation process for generic DPI products. The list of FDA-Approved Dry Powder Inhalers and Corresponding Equivalence Testing Requirements Based on FDA Product-Specific Guidance are tabulated in Table 5.

Among the digital dry powder inhalers currently approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), the Digihaler® platform represents a significant advancement in inhalation therapy. This technology has been incorporated into products such as ProAir® Digihaler® (approved in 2018), AirDuo® Digihaler® (2019), and Armonair® Digihaler® (2020). Each device integrates an electronic module (eModule) equipped with a digital sensor that captures critical usage metrics, including date and time of actuation, peak inspiratory flow (PIF), inhalation volume, and other parameters indicative of inhalation technique. Additionally, these devices can provide real-time feedback and reminders to support

adherence. From a regulatory standpoint, the incorporation of digital features into DPIs reflects growing interest in leveraging digital health technologies to enhance therapeutic outcomes and ensure proper device use. While the full clinical and economic impact of digital DPIs is still being evaluated, early data suggest potential benefits in improving medication adherence, optimizing technique, and enabling remote monitoring. Continued post-market surveillance and real-world evidence generation will be essential to fully characterize the value and reliability of such devices within routine clinical practice^[34].

Table 5: List of FDA-Approved Dry Powder Inhalers (DPIs) and Corresponding Equivalence Testing Requirements Based on FDA Product-Specific Guidance

S.No	Product / Combination	RLD Name	In Vitro Tests	In Vivo (Fasting)	Clinical Endpoint Study
1.	Fluticasone Propionate Inhalation Powder	Flovent diskus	Single Actuation Content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD) Realistic APSD Dissolution Particle morphology of the emitted dose	Fasting Single-dose, two-way crossover	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
2.	Fluticasone Furoate (monotherapy)	Arnuity ellipta	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD)	Fasting: Single-dose,two-way crossover and Single-dose	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
3.	Umeclidinium Bromide (monotherapy)	Incruse ellipta	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD)	Fasting: Single-dose,two-way crossover and Single-dose	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
4.	Mometasone Furoate Inhalation Powder	Asmanex twisthaler	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD)	Fasting: Single-dose,two-way crossover	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
5.	Salmeterol Xinafoate Powder (monotherapy)	Serevent	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD) Realistic APSD Particle morphology of the emitted dose	Fasting (Single-dose, two-way crossover) Single-dose, two-way crossover with charcoal block	One comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
6.	Tiotropium Bromide Inhalation Powder	Spiriva	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD) Realistic APSD Particle morphology of the emitted dose	Fasting (Single-dose, two-way crossover) Single-dose, two-way crossover with charcoal block	One comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study

S.No	Product / Combination	RLD Name	In Vitro Tests	In Vivo (Fasting)	Clinical Endpoint Study
7.	Fluticasone Propionate + Salmeterol Xinofoate	Advair diskus	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD) Realistic APSD Dissolution Particle morphology of the emitted dose	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover Single-dose, two-way crossover with charcoal block	Two in vitro bioequivalence studies, one in vivo bioequivalence study with pharmacokinetic endpoints, and one comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study One comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence Study- Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
8.	Fluticasone Furoate+ Vilanterol Trifenatate	Breo ellipta	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD)	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
9.	Fluticasone Furoate+ Umeclidinium + Vilanterol	Trelegy ellipta	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD)	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
10.	Umeclidinium + Vilanterol	Anoro ellipta	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD)	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
11.	Acclidinium bromide	Tudorza pressair	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD)	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
12.	Acclidinium bromide; Formoterol fumarate	Duaklir pressair	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD)	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
13.	Albuterol sulfate EQ 0.09 mg Base/inh	Proair respiclick	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD)	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study
14.	Budesonide 0.08 mg/inh, 0.16 mg/inh	Pulmicort flexhaler	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD)	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover	Comparative clinical endpoint bioequivalence study

S.No	Product / Combination	RLD Name	In Vitro Tests	In Vivo (Fasting)	Clinical Endpoint Study
15.	Levodopa	Inbrija	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD) Evaluation of crystalline and amorphous content of the powder formulation	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover	Not applicable
16.	Loxapine	Adasuve	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD) Evaluation of crystalline and amorphous content of the powder formulation	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover	Not applicable
17.	Tobramycin	Tobi podhaler	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD) Realistic APSD	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover Particle morphology of the emitted dose Evaluation of crystalline and amorphous content of the powder formulation	Not applicable
18.	Treprostinil	Tyvaso dpi	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD) Realistic APSD	Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover Fasting: Single-dose, two-way crossover with charcoal block Particle morphology of the emitted dose	Not applicable
19.	Zanamivir	Relenza	Single actuation content (SAC) Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD) Realistic APSD Polymorphic form of the drug substance Particle morphology of the emitted dose	Not applicable	Not applicable

Figure 4: Illustration of Product life cycle of Dry Powder Inhalers

CONCLUSION:

Next generation dry powder inhalers relies heavily on precise and robust characterization techniques to ensure consistent performance and therapeutic efficacy. Innovations in formulation, device design, and analytical methods are essential to be closely aligned with evolving regulatory expectations, particularly those set by the FDA, to support bioequivalence, quality, and patient safety. This review demonstrates the critical role of in vitro, ex vivo and in vivo performance testing, along with comprehensive critical manufacturing, and controls documentation, in the development of next-generation DPIs. Thorough advanced characterization remains central to the successful design, regulation, and clinical translation of future pulmonary drug delivery systems. This review offered a unified perspective on the development of next-generation DPIs that are effective, safe and aligned with patient needs and global regulatory expectations.

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None to declare.

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